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ABSTRACTS

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Secondary Metabolites for New Age Potent Bio-Pesticides Formulations

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Abstract: There are many obstacles in the way of extracting terpenoids from neem, such as problems with yield and purity and the high cost of doing so on a wide scale. In addition to complicating matters, batch-to-batch variability makes it challenging to establish repeatable and consistent bioactivity. In addition, addressing market demand for biomasses with a low carbon impact presents scalability challenges. An alternate strategy to overcome these obstacles is to produce high-value neem compounds by using heterologous hosts like *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* or *Escherichia coli*. Known to be usually safe, these hosts have the potential to be more functional and high-quality than those that use more conventional extraction techniques. The functional characterization of terpene genes involved in isoprenoid biosynthesis is the main goal of the proposed study. Using concepts from synthetic biology, the goal is to maximize production in metabolically tractable heterologous systems, including bacteria and in vitro and in vivo plant systems. This approach holds promise for overcoming the limitations of large-scale extraction and providing a more controlled and scalable method for meeting the market demand for neem chemicals.

Keywords: Neem, terpenoids, secondary metabolite, functional characterization.

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